

MODERN TEACHING METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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***Abstract:** This article focuses on productive types of speech activity, which is especially important for mastering a foreign language. The Article specifies how effective work with special texts in a foreign language helps to formulate the necessary language and communication skills for students in a non-native language and promotes the development of their common scientific knowledge and skills.*

Today the professional language teacher has a good grounding in the various techniques and new approaches, and they know and understand the history and evolution of teaching methodologies. The modern teacher will in fact use a variety of methodologies and approaches, choosing techniques from each method that they consider effective and applying them according to the learning context and objectives. Therefore, each new proposal must undergo a thorough examination and be publicly discussed by the scientific and pedagogical community. Nowadays there is a great variety of methods of teaching foreign languages. This article presents an overview of some modern methods and techniques used in TFL.

Modernization of education is a large-scale program of the state, within which a plan of competitive measures should be developed and implemented. Modernization is the updating and improvement of the existing education system. With any modernization of education, there are several problems. The first is to preserve the positive that exists in the existing system; the second - if something useful for society was lost in education for previous years, then it is necessary to restore it; the third, the main one, is to bring the education system in line with the demands of the society.

In recent decades, linguists and methodologists have shown great interest in the subject-linguistic approach in teaching foreign languages. In the light of the current trends in the expansion of intercultural dialogue and the globalization of the educational space, the study of the language is of particular relevance, oriented to its practical application: a student-foreigner needs not just the mastery of the language in

everyday, everyday communication, but, above all, his use in the professional sphere of communication. An effective search for necessary scientific literature on the specialty, preparation of abstracts and reports on scientific topics, communication with colleagues, etc. All this is a strong motivating factor in learning a foreign language.

Another technique that synthesizes these postulates was the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) methodology, proposed in 1996 by a group of European linguists (UNICOM, University of Jyväskylä). The methodology of subject-language integrated education is widespread and successfully practiced in many European universities and is aimed at both teaching the language and maintaining the subject. CLIL is an educational approach in which certain scientific disciplines or separate sections are taught through a foreign language with a double practical output, namely: by studying the content of a particular discipline in conjunction with the simultaneous improvement of a foreign language [1].

CLIL describes an evolving approach to teaching and learning where subjects are taught and studied through the medium of a non-native language. The experience of learning subjects through the medium of a non –native language is more challenging and intensive as there is more exposure to the language and learners acquire knowledge and skills in different areas of the curriculum. In CLIL, learning a curriculum subject in a second, third or sometimes fourth language involves drawing on effective pedagogical practice from a range of different educational contexts. Curriculum subjects apart from languages are taught through the target language. These include Art, Geography, history, Information and communication technology (ICT), Mathematics, Science, Social Science.

There are many advantages to the CLIL approach: it develops confident learners and enhances academic cognitive processes and communication skills. CLIL encourages intercultural understanding and community values. In addition, research shows that learners become more sensitive to vocabulary and ideas presented in their first language as well as in the target language, learners reach proficiency levels in all four skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing.

The main linguistic guideline in the CLIL methodology is a special text, based on the study and elaboration of which the above goals are achieved. The text as a source of information introduces the reader to a certain topic, and serves as the basis for a lexico-grammatical module that assures the assimilation of scientific terminology and certain grammatical and structural-stylistic constructions. The text is also a starting point for conducting discussions and expanding the language material on a given topic while at the same time contributing to the formation and activation of communicative skills in dialogical and monolog speech. Thus, the methodology of language-based

integrated teaching of a foreign language encompasses the main types of speech activity, contributes to the increase of students' activity in the learning process, develops their language competence, induces polylingual interests and raises educational motivation. Principles of subject-language integrated learning. Based on the analysis of foreign and Uzbek studies, as well as our own pedagogical experience, we developed the following pedagogical principles of the CLIL method: 1. The principle of using a rich, from the cognitive point of view, authentic educational material. The basic requirements for educational materials are authenticity, information richness and a certain degree of cognitive load. Interactive authentic materials have not only a high motivating potential, but can also be used as a basis for creating an artificial language environment and assignments with a high degree of cognitive difficulty. The teacher actively uses a foreign language, acting as a "language model" for students. 2. The principle of active support and assistance of the teacher in the learning process. For successful achievement of the set goals, the student needs to receive support from the teacher. With the development of his foreign language competence, the amount and intensity of assistance from the teacher gradually decreases. Using this principle will reduce cognitive and linguistic loads when studying unfamiliar content in a foreign language. The tasks that the teacher proposes should be supplemented with certain explanations that will allow students to successfully cope with the tasks set. Much attention is paid to productive types of speech activity, which is especially important for mastering a foreign language. 3. Principle of intensive and productive possession of a foreign language. Problem training offers a large number of methodical techniques and is aimed at the active use of authentic communication within the framework of a training session, since instruction in foreign languages is most successful in the presence of communicative goals and a meaningful communication situation.

One of the main characteristics of problem training is the use of the so-called "gaps" principle, according to which authentic communication will take place only if there are certain communicative gaps. Teachers can use this method to create authentic communicative situations, because, by performing similar tasks, students actively interact with each other. 4. Principle of multiculturalism. The CLIL methodology makes it possible to consider all sorts of topics from different cultural positions, taking into account the differences in the perception of many things among representatives of certain cultures. 5. The principle of development of higher-order thinking skills. The development of higher-order thinking skills is the key to success in the modern information society. In the Bloom taxonomy [4], the list of cognitive processes and pedagogical goals are organized hierarchically from the simple to the complex, from Low Order Thinking Skills to the cognitive processes of the higher order (High Order

Thinking Skills). According to the taxonomy of Bloom, the student cannot realize the concept, first not remembering it, and cannot apply knowledge if he does not understand what is at stake. According to this theory, the teacher should ask students questions that stimulate the development of low-level thought processes (LOT) (special questions beginning with what, when, where and which). It is also necessary to include issues that develop more complex analysis and assessment skills (HOT). This group can include issues beginning with the words why and how, which mean when formulating answers using more complex language structures. The interaction of content, thinking and language, the ability to adequately expound complex thought processes is not automatically formed, but requires systematic development and training, both in native and in the studied foreign language. 6. The principle of sustainable learning. Stable training is understood as follows: the teacher should make sure that during the learning process, the long-term memory of students has been activated and the knowledge that they received during the lesson will pass from the passive to the asset.

In the CLIL concept, sustainable training is of paramount importance, since the teacher contributes both to the study of professional content and directly to the foreign language. In the same way, the teacher needs to develop ways of testing and assessing the ability of students to adequately communicate on professional topics in the first (L1) and second language (L2) [4].

Indeed, real education should not be forced or manipulated, freedom of education supposed to be free from physical and psychological pressure, and it is an important tool of reaching the success in all fields of society. Giving an opportunity to every single youth to find him in the field that was chosen at the doors of University is the most important target of higher education.

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